

Creature Close-ups

Scientists studying the seabed often divide the living things into different groups based on their size. Some creatures are collected by sieving through mud and sand; the size of the holes in the sieve will sort them.

‘Macrofauna’ are usually too small to be caught in a regular net but they can be sorted by using a fine sieve where the holes are just 0.3-0.5mm wide!

Can you match the creature close-up with the right animal?

Ophiopholis aculeata (Brittle star):

Porania pulvillus (Starfish):

Stenopleustes latipes (Amphipod):

Munida sarsi (Decapod):

Image credit: Georgios Kazanidis / ATLAS

These ‘Macrofauna’ (or ‘Macrobenthos’) were collected from the Mingulay Reef Complex in Scotland. To work out what they are, a scientist has taken close-up pictures of particular body parts. The creatures have been preserved, so their colours have faded.